

Conductive Hearing Loss & Ear Infections

*Understanding and managing
the effects of
children's hearing loss,
caused by*

Otitis Media

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A Guide for Families & Teachers

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Want to know more about the social and educational outcomes of listening problems? Go to:

www.eartroubles.com

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Middle ear disease (Otitis Media) is an illness experienced by most children while growing up. When children suffer from middle ear disease it can affect their hearing, resulting in Conductive Hearing Loss. Persistent hearing loss can affect children's behaviour and development. Children's behaviour at home, at school, and on the sports ground, may give clues to listening problems. This resource will help you to identify the problem so you can take steps to prevent and manage the illness and its effects.

How do we hear with a healthy ear?

- Sound is caught by the outside part of the ear (outer ear) and moves down the ear canal to the ear drum.
- The sound makes the eardrum vibrate and in turn the small bones in the middle ear vibrate.
- The small bones then help send the sound on to the inner ear and the brain.
- The brain then works out what the sound is.

What is Otitis Media?

- Children pick up middle ear infection very easily – often following having a sore throat or a common cold.
- The infection causes fluid to build up in the middle ear.
 - Too much fluid in the ear can put pressure on the ear drum and cause it to burst, resulting in a sticky discharge.

What is Conductive Hearing Loss?

- Children with Otitis Media often suffer from poor hearing. Conductive Hearing Loss occurs when fluid in the middle ear or a hole in the ear drum prevents sound from passing freely through the ear.
- Many young children have Conductive Hearing Loss, particularly in Aboriginal communities.
- If repeated ear infections are untreated, children may have long-term hearing loss.

..and it comes and goes

- Conductive Hearing Loss comes and goes in a way that is hard to detect as it is not always painful to the child.
- Children with Conductive Hearing Loss may cope when it is quiet, or when they are talking about a familiar topic with someone they know.
- Having trouble listening some of the time or in poor listening conditions makes some people think 'they can hear if they want to'. This is usually not the case.

IDENTIFYING CHILDREN WITH LISTENING PROBLEMS

What to look out for

Difficulties at home and at school

If you think a child is being difficult or naughty, it may be due to their poor hearing. Understanding what to look for in children's behaviour, at home and at school, may help you identify and manage listening problems.

At home

Children with Conductive Hearing Loss:

- May not understand or respond to what is said to them
- Can be easily frustrated and naughty
- May come home from school feeling tired and bad tempered, from having to work so hard to listen in class
- May be demanding, argue a lot and/or sulk.

At childcare and school

Children with Conductive Hearing Loss:

- Will find it hard to hear when it is noisy
- May be seen as aggressive, over indulged or over sensitive
- May often be in trouble at school, or be quiet, shy or anxious
- May have difficulty learning to read and spell
- May have problems playing team sports because they cannot hear other players or the coach.

Feeling confused

- Kids with listening problems may have trouble hearing and following instructions.
- Seeing other children who understand what to do may make them feel 'dumb'.
- They may worry a lot about not being able to do things or getting things wrong, and may try hard to do the right thing.
- They may experience more stress, especially when it is noisy.
- They often feel rejected or left out of social groups when it is hard for them to hear what people are saying.
- Children with Conductive Hearing Loss who are quiet and shy may worry about meeting new people.

Covering up

Children with hearing problems may compensate for feeling dumb, anxious or embarrassed. This behaviour can annoy parents and teachers, and get them into trouble.

Behaviour in children to look out for:

- Teasing others, especially when it's noisy at school
- Talking when it's quiet (so they can hear other children's replies)
- Talking constantly to avoid being shamed because they do not understand
- Bossing others, as this can be a way to control what is happening.

(Note some children with auditory processing problems without any current hearing loss may also respond in the ways described above).

Playing 'Blind Man's Simon Says'

This game can help to screen children for possible hearing loss.

- If in a childcare or classroom group setting, select four or five children.
- Be sure to select a mix of children in each group, including some who you believe have good hearing.
- It is best to play the game without other children watching to avoid those who have difficulties being teased.
- Firstly, explain the rules - these are that you will ask them to shut their eyes and then ask them to do some things, often in a very quiet voice. They don't have to wait for you to say 'Simon Says'.
- The children participating stand at the front of the room, while you stand about 2-3 meters away in front of them.
- Try to minimise the background noise during the game.

Step One

Start the game by saying, one at a time, all the instructions you are going to use in a loud, clear voice to ensure all the children can perform the tasks.

Below is a list of instructions you can use.

- Put your hand on your nose
- Put your hand on your hair
- Put your hand on your cheek
- Put your hand in the air
- Put your hand on your ears
- Put your hand on your chin
- Put your hand on your knee

Be sure to vary the order that these instructions are given so children cannot predict what they are going to be asked to do next.

Step Two

- After all the children have demonstrated that they can follow these instructions when they are given in a loud voice, tell the students that you are now going to say them quietly.
- Dropping your voice, but not whispering, give an instruction.
- You can play this game with a single child if you have another adult whose hearing is known to be OK. They stand beside the child and follow the instructions so you know your voice level is loud enough to be just heard.
- When playing the game with a group of children use the children participating to check your voice level. If all the children have difficulty hearing you then you know you need to raise your voice level. The children in the group with normal hearing confirm for you that you can be heard. This is why it is vital that the game is not played only with children whose hearing is suspect.

HEARING LOSS AND FAMILIES

Children with hearing loss can be alternately demanding and clingy with parents. Brothers and sisters may resent children getting what seems like too much parental attention through the focus on treatment of their ear infections or because of their behaviour problems and/or their greater need for social and emotional support from parents. Communication problems related to persistent otitis media can result in parents finding it harder to engage emotionally with their child.

As a result they may feel they are being a bad parent. This can be compounded by others blaming children's hearing related social difficulties on poor parenting. This kind of 'self-blame' or being blamed by others is often misinformed and destructive. It is not uncommon for some parents of children with persistent ear disease to experience depression.

Parenting children experiencing persistent ear infections and Conductive Hearing Loss is more demanding. It is important to seek and accept available help, as well as taking care of your own wellbeing as a parent. Tell family, friends and teachers about the outcomes of Conductive Hearing Loss described in this booklet.

More information is available at www.eartroubles.com.

DIFFICULTIES SOMETIMES, IN SOME PLACES

Families and teachers of children with hearing difficulties can become confused when the child appears to have problems only with some types of activity, or only in some places.

The level of a child's hearing loss can fluctuate with ear disease (otitis media). Also, social difficulties caused by hearing loss can vary, depending on the situation. A child may be perfectly happy and comfortable in a familiar situation with people he or she knows well. Yet social difficulties may quickly become evident when the child is faced with a new situation or some sort of challenge.

Situations that present challenges include:

- a new teacher or school;
- a change of class or joining a new social group, at school or elsewhere;
- a change in the membership of an existing or known social group;
- an absence of the usual family, teacher or peer support; and
- any need to participate in activities where the child may fear shame or exclusion.

With some children, social difficulties and behavioural problems may be most apparent at school, where children must listen more, where greater social conformity is expected and where background noise levels may often be high in classrooms. Unfortunately, teachers may mistakenly attribute the resulting school behavioural and social difficulties to 'family problems' outside school.

There can also be a 'rebound and release' effect when the child returns home from school. The stress and frustrations of a day spent trying hard to hear, comply and cope at school can lead to tantrums or uncooperative behaviour at home. A student who is an 'angel' at school but sometimes a 'devil' at home may be experiencing hearing related anxiety and frustration.

When parents and teachers understand the interaction between hearing loss, listening demands and background noise levels, they can collaborate to more effectively support and assist a child with hearing or auditory processing problems.

When a child is displaying anxiety and/or inappropriate social behaviour related to listening problems, he or she may benefit from:

- a quiet time after any period with heavy listening demands;
- a quiet time at home after school;
- someone to talk to about the reasons for, and their reactions to, social stress and anxiety; and
- routines that foster relaxation and a sense of control.

How schools can help

- Improve classroom acoustics.
- Carry out professional development for teachers on this issue – talk to local hearing advisory teachers about what is available also see www.eartroubles.com.
- Use teaching that supports multi-sensory learning by students.
- Consider if Conductive Hearing Loss may be contributing to school behaviour and learning problems for some children.
- Conduct classroom screenings to identify children that have hearing difficulties (see the activity Blind Man's Simon Says on the next page, or: www.eartroubles.com/index.php/blind_mans_simon_says).
- If there are indications of Conductive Hearing Loss refer children for ear health and hearing checks.

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Social problems

Anxiety and shyness

Learning problems

Difficulties with change...

*Can all be related to
children having*

Conductive Hearing Loss

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